

THE ROLE OF JOB CRAFTING IN MEDIATING THE EFFECTS OF LEADERSHIP STYLE AND WORK ENVIRONMENT ON TEACHER PERFORMANCE IN HIGH SCHOOLS OF MEDAN CITY, INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to determine the direct and indirect effects of leadership style and work environment on teacher performance through job crafting. This study uses quantitative analysis. The sample used in this study consisted of 540 high school teachers in Medan City who came from schools with accreditation A. This sample was obtained from the results of filling out a questionnaire through the Googleform application. The data analysis used is SEM-PLS. The results of the study show that leadership style, work environment, and job crafting directly have a significant effect on teacher performance in high schools of Medan City. It is also shown that leadership style and work environment have a significant effect on job crafting for high school teachers in Medan City. In addition, job crafting is indirectly able to mediate the effects of the two variables, i.e. leadership style and work environment on teacher performance in high schools of Medan City.

Keyword: teacher performance, leadership style, work environment, job crafting

1. INTRODUCTION

In any country in the world, if the nation wants to progress, it cannot be separated from the world of education. Therefore human resources must be taken seriously. Without fostering or educating the people to produce reliable human resources, the country concerned will continue to be left behind. At present Indonesia is or has begun to make changes and developments in the economic, social, cultural and political aspects, especially in the field of education. A strong nation and state must be built through educational development that prepares people to face and respond to existing challenges. Chapter 1 Article 1 Paragraph 1 of the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System defines that: "Education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students can develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and the skills they need." As part of efforts to achieve national education goals, Bangun (2016) explains that education is becoming more relevant both in terms of the number of graduates and the talent needed for development. Changes to educational institutions (schools) must be carried out in accordance with the policies above them. These policies can be macro- or micro-management in nature. Whether

for macro- or micro-management, there should be an organic managerial function at the top of the organizational hierarchy. These functions include planning, organizing, leading, and controlling. All this must be done in order to achieve its main goal. The following table shows the number of high schools in 10 provinces on Sumatra Island (Even Semester Academic Year).

Table 1: The Number of High Schools in 10 Provinces on Sumatra Island (Even Semester Academic Year)

Province	AY 2016/2017	AY 2017/2018	AY 2018/2019	AY 2019/2020	AY 2020/2021
Aceh	535	524	530	527	532
North Sumatra	1.081	1.076	1.090	1.061	1077
West Sumatra	331	326	330	330	330
Riau	459	447	447	453	456
Jambi	237	225	234	236	236
South Sumatra	612	597	591	594	603
Lampung	513	489	503	507	513
Bengkulu	144	139	141	141	142
Bangka Belitung Islands	70	68	70	71	70
Riau Islands	158	138	145	150	152

Source: <http://statistik.data.kemdikbud.go.id/> (2021)

Particularly in Medan City, the growth in the number of private high schools has fluctuated from year to year, while the number of public high schools has always remained the same as can be seen in the table below.

Table 2. The Number of High Schools in Medan City

Academic Year		Public	Private
2016/2017	Odd	21	196
	Even	21	194
2017/2018	Odd	21	196
	Even	21	197
2018/2019	Odd	21	199
	Even	21	200
2019/2020	Odd	21	196
	Even	21	194
2020/2021	Odd	21	200
	Even	21	200

Source: <https://dapo.dikdasmen.kemdikbud.go.id/sp/1/070000> (2021)

Teachers are expected to have four competencies, namely pedagogic, personality, professional, and social competencies, in order to fulfill their role as learning agent teachers whose main responsibility is to improve the quality of national education (Article 3 of Government

Regulation No. 74 of 2008). According to Government Regulation no. 32 of 2013, educators must have academic qualifications and competencies as learning agents, physically and mentally healthy, and able to contribute to achieving national education development goals.

Medan, as the 3rd largest city in Indonesia after Jakarta and Surabaya, shows statistics on the pedagogic and professional competence of teachers as shown in the following table.

Table 3. Pedagogic and Professional Competencies Test of Teachers in 5 Big Cities in Indonesia

City	Pedagogic Competency	Profesional Competency
DKI Jakarta	56.74	65.09
Surabaya	57.85	65.90
Medan	50.83	58.66
Bandung	58.79	65.97
Makassar	51.69	58.76

Source: Regional Education Balance

Purwanto (2010) emphasized that the teacher is the most important factor in the world of education. Therefore, the teacher's work environment must be evaluated seriously because the teacher's work environment will be associated with various elements, including job satisfaction, morale, and motivation. According to Hasibuan (2014), based on data from the Ministry of Education and Culture, the number of high school teachers in Medan City tends to increase from year to year, especially in private high schools. Meanwhile, public high school teachers tend to be stable over the last five years. The total number of high school teachers can be seen in the table below.

Table 4. The Number of High School Teachers in Medan City

Academic Year	Public	Private	Total
2016/2017	1,353	2,444	3,797
2017/2018	1,350	2,657	4,007
2018/2019	1,360	2,658	4,018
2019/2020	1,290	2,808	4,098
2020/2021	1,398	3,090	4,488

Source: <https://dapo.dikdasmen.kemdikbud.go.id/sp/1/070000> (2021)

From Table 4 above, it can be concluded that in general the number of high school teachers has increased per academic year in Medan City.

Furthermore, it can be seen in the image below that the qualifications of high school teachers in Medan City from 2016 to 2019 are relatively stable. Approximately 96% are dominated by teachers with educational backgrounds above D4 or S1.

Figure 1. Diagram of the Qualifications of Educators in High Schools of Medan City
(Source: Regional Education Balance)

The diagram above shows that the number and educational qualifications of teaching staff in Medan City are relatively stable, where educators with educational levels below D4/S1 are only around 4%. However, the condition of this educational qualification is in contrast to the pedagogic competence and professionalism of teaching staff, which is still far from what was expected.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Teacher Performance

According to Mangkunegara (2019: 31), the term performance comes from the word job performance or actual performance (work achievement or actual achievement achieved by a person), namely the work results in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties according to the responsibilities assigned to him. Furthermore, according to Tannady (2017: 154) performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee or a department or an organization in carrying out its tasks and targets according to the responsibilities assigned to it within a certain evaluation period. Employee performance is the result of implementing an organization's goals, therefore good performance is an important thing for all employees to do. Employee performance is the result in quality and quantity that is achieved by an employee in carrying out tasks in accordance with the responsibilities that have been assigned (Mangkunegara, 2017: 67). Furthermore, according to Bernadin and Russel

(in Sapitri, 2016: 5), performance is a record of the outcomes resulting from the function of a particular job or activity during a certain period of time.

Employee performance dimensions and indicators according to Sedarmayanti (2010: 263) are as follows:

1. Work achievement. The indicators are working skills, the potential for knowledge development through training, and the right completion of work in accordance with the time.
2. Skill. The indicators are the ability of the employee and his educational background.
3. Behavior. The indicators are employee attitudes at work, employee loyalty, and relationships with fellow employees.

2.2 Leadership

Leadership is the process of getting people to do their best to achieve the desired results. It can be described as the ability to convince others to behave differently. Leadership also involves developing and communicating a vision for the future.

According to Robbins & Coulter (2012), leadership is the process of influencing a group towards achieving goals, whereas according to Armstrong (2016), leadership is the process of getting people to do their best to achieve the desired results. Another definition according to Schermerhorn (2013) is that leadership is the process of inspiring others to work hard to complete important tasks.

Yuki in Gunawan (2015) says that leadership is a process to influence others to understand and agree with what needs to be done and how the task is done effectively, as well as a process to facilitate individual and group efforts to achieve common goals.

Based on some of the opinions of the experts stated above, it appears that leadership is the behavior of an individual who leads an activity where the leader tries to influence other people so that they are willing to work together to achieve organizational goals.

The broad definition of leadership includes the process of influencing in determining organizational goals, motivating the behavior of followers to achieve goals, influencing the interpretation of events faced by followers, maintaining cooperative relationships and group work, and obtaining support and cooperation from people outside the group or organization. From the definitions above, it can be seen that leadership is an important part of management, where a leader must be able to create harmonious integration with his subordinates as well as fostering cooperation, directing and encouraging the work passion of subordinates, influencing and providing attitudes and behavior of individuals and groups, thus forming the leadership style that the leader applies (Kamal, Winarso, and Sulistio, 2019).

2.3 Work Environment

A conducive work environment greatly influences the teacher in working where with a safe and good environment he can work in peace. This is in accordance with what was stated by

Sudrajat (2014) that the work environment is everything that is around the worker and that can affect him in carrying out the tasks assigned to him. So that in this way the teacher can be safe and secure in carrying out his duties and this is also in accordance with what was stated by Alrub (2015) who argued that the work environment is a variable that predicts the level of intention to keep working. The work environment will affect employee performance which is in line with what McCoy & Evans (2015) stated that the physical environment provides a potentially powerful intervention tool for improving organized work.

Thus the work environment is a variable that is an integral part of comfortable and regular work when employees carry out their work activities. The definition of the work environment according to Nawawi (2012) is everything that is around the workers and that can affect them in carrying out the tasks assigned, for example cleanliness, music, lighting, and others.

The work environment that describes the good or bad of an organization in the field of government can be interpreted as everything that is around employees that directly or indirectly influences the implementation of their work. According to Sutrisno (2012), the work environment is the overall work facilities and infrastructure that exist around employees that can influence the implementation of work. Maryati (2014) explained that a healthy and good work environment will affect the comfort of employees' work. If the work or employees feel comfortable at work, productivity will certainly increase.

From the description above, it can be concluded that the work environment cannot be considered trivial or mediocre if you really want the employee or worker to do their job well and perfectly.

2.4 Job Crafting

If someone works, so that his work runs smoothly and better, he tries or takes the initiative to do it so that he can carry out his duties more quickly and precisely. This is in accordance with what was stated by Tims, Bakker, and Derks (2012) who argued that job crafting is a form of change made by employees on their own initiative to balance demands and resources at work. According to Berg and Dutton (Tims, Bakker, and Derks, 2012), job crafting is changing jobs in such a way according to preferences, skills, and abilities of employees so as to increase job satisfaction. Furthermore, according to Kirkendall (2013), job crafting is a way in which an individual changes aspects and perceptions of work to adapt it to the characteristics of the job and the needs of the employees themselves.

According to Slemp and Brodrick (2014), job crafting is a way in which employees have an active role at work by making changes both physically and cognitively. Job crafting is informal, namely focusing on changes in a positive direction. Employees create initiatives based on their interests, values, and satisfaction. Job crafting is also a form of individual wisdom from work experience to fulfill needs and desires. This is almost the same as what was conveyed by Grant and Ashford (in Slemp and Bodrick, 2014), which is a form of proactive behavior that encourages employees to do better.

Petrou, Demerouti and Schaufeli (2015) define job crafting as the initiative and willingness of employees to reconstruct aspects of their work with the aim of improving their working conditions. This is done by exploring sources of information (asking superiors or colleagues for advice), seeking challenges (asking for more responsibility), and reducing demands (removing the emotional, mental, or physical pressure or demands from work).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The approach used in this study is the Structured Equation Model (SEM). The population in this study consisted of all high school teachers in Medan City totaling 4,845, consisting of 1,381 public high school teachers and 3,464 private high school teachers. The sample locations, namely schools, were determined using the non-probability sampling method, specifically the purposive sampling technique. In this case, a school was determined to be the sample provided that it had achieved Accreditation A. Using the Slovin formula, 369 teachers were obtained as a sample which was confirmed based on the results of filling out the questionnaire through the Google form application.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Respondents' Description

a. Description of Respondents by Gender

The general description of the respondents in this study were high school teachers, both public and private, in Medan City, obtained from the results of filling out a questionnaire through the Googleform application. The general description of the respondents in this study were high school teachers, both public and private, in Medan City, obtained from the results of filling out a questionnaire through the Googleform application.

Figure 2. Characteristics of Respondents by Gender

From Figure 2 above it can be seen that of the 369 respondents, 247 respondents (67%) were women, while 122 respondents were men (33%). This shows that in Medan City there are more female teachers than male teachers. It shows that the maternal nature of female teachers emerges in educating their students at school.

b. Description of Respondents by Education Level

The general description of the respondents in this study were high school teachers, both public and private, in Medan City, obtained from the results of filling out a questionnaire through the Googleform application, and a schematic diagram of their distribution by education level is shown in the following figure.

Figure 3. Characteristics of Respondents by Education Level

From Figure 3 above it is known that among high school teachers in Medan City none have a high school education level or 0%, 66 or 18% are diploma graduates, 221 or 60% are bachelor (S1) graduates, 52 or 14% are magister (S2) graduates, and 30 or 8% are doctoral (S3) graduates..

c. Description of Respondents by Age

The general description of the respondents in this study were high school teachers, both public and private, in Medan City, obtained from the results of filling out a questionnaire through the Googleform application, and a schematic diagram of their distribution by age is shown in the following figure.

Figure 4. Characteristics of Respondents by Age

Based on Figure 4 above, it is known that out of the high school teachers as many as 73 (20%) are aged <25 years, 58 (16%) are aged 25-35 years, 129 (35%) are aged 36-45, and 108 (29 %) are aged 46-59 years. This can be interpreted that more teachers at the age of 35-45 years carry out their profession as teachers in high schools in Medan City.

4.2 Measurement Model Analysis (Outer Model)

a. Convergent Validity Test

The results of the convergent validity test of the data instruments in this study are shown in the following table:

Table 5. Loading Factor

The image shows two screenshots of the SmartPLS software interface, specifically the 'Outer Loadings' section. The top screenshot displays the loading factors for a measurement model with indicators EP1-EP7 and JE1-JE6. The bottom screenshot displays the loading factors for a measurement model with indicators LS1-LS6 and WE1-WE7. All loading factors are highlighted in green, indicating they are above the recommended threshold of 0.5.

Indicator	Employee...	Job Erafti...	Leadershi...	Work Env...
EP1	0.745			
EP2	0.832			
EP3	0.799			
EP4	0.797			
EP5	0.733			
EP6	0.760			
EP7	0.779			
JE1		0.822		
JE2		0.762		
JE3		0.754		
JE4		0.831		
JE5		0.744		
JE6		0.796		

Indicator	Employee...	Job Erafti...	Leadershi...	Work Env...
LS1			0.752	
LS2			0.820	
LS3			0.745	
LS4			0.781	
LS5			0.743	
LS6			0.856	
WE1				0.751
WE2				0.751
WE3				0.759
WE4				0.772
WE5				0.780
WE6				0.738
WE7				0.761

From the table above it appears that the loading factor value is more significant than 0.7, so that all existing items can be declared valid.

b. Discriminant Validity Test

The results of the discriminant validity test of the data in this study are shown in the following table.

Table 6. Discriminant Validity

	Job Erafting_	Leadership Style_	Teacher Performance_	Work Env...
Job Erafting_	0.780			
Leadership Style_	0.923	0.784		
Teacher Performance_	0.946	0.932	0.779	
Work Environment_	0.949	0.920	0.932	0.759

From table 6 above, the model has good discriminant validity if each loading indicator value of a latent variable is greater than that of other correlated variables. The cross-loading value in this study for each indicator is greater than the other latent variables. This shows that each variable has good discriminant validity.

c. Construct Reliability Test

The results of the construct reliability test of data in this study are as shown in the following table.

Table 7. Construct Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracte...
Job Erafting_	0.892	0.894	0.916	0.609
Leadership Style_	0.874	0.875	0.905	0.615
Teacher Performance_	0.891	0.892	0.915	0.606
Work Environment_	0.877	0.878	0.905	0.576

Based on Table 7 above, it can be seen that the average value is > 0.5 , then the composite reliability value is > 0.905 . So it can be concluded that the indicators in the study can measure well.

4.3 Measurement Model Analysis (Inner Model)

Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

The calculation results for the R-Square value are as shown in the following table.

Table 8. R-Square Value

The screenshot shows the SPSS 'R Square' output window. The title bar indicates the file name 'Sampel bisa 369, var 4 kues 7,7,7,7 =28.txt' and the current view '*SAMPEL 369, VAR 4.s'. The main content area displays a table with the following data:

Matrix	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Job Crafting_	0.917	0.917
Teacher Performance_	0.921	0.921

Based on Table 8 above, it was found that the value of R-Square Adjusted for the job crafting variable was 0.917 or 91.7%, while the remaining 8.3% was not examined in this study, while for teacher performance variables the value of R-Square Adjusted is 0.921 or 92.1%, the remaining 7.9% is not examined in this study.

4.4 Predictive Relevance (Q^2)

The value of Q^2 has the same meaning as the coefficient of determination R-Square. The value of Q-square (Q^2) is greater than 0 indicating the model has predictive relevance. On the other hand, the value of Q^2 is less than 0 indicating that the model has less predictive relevance or in other words, if all the values of Q^2 are higher, the model is considered to be more compatible with the data. Calculation of the value of Q^2 can be done as follows.

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1-R^2_1)(1-R^2_2) \dots (R_n^2)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1-0.917)(1-0.921)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (0.083)(0.079)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - 0.0066$$

$$Q^2 = 0.9934$$

Based on the results of the analysis, it was found that the value of Q^2 was 0.9934. So it can be concluded that all the variables in this study, namely teacher performance, leadership style, work environment, and job crafting contributed 99.34% to the original data in the existing

structural model. Then the remaining 0.66% needs to be developed apart from this research variable.

4.5 Effect Size (F2)

Effect size (F2) is determining the kindness of the model and also to find out whether the predictor variable has a weak, sufficient or strong effect at the structural level.

4.6 Hypothesis Test

Table 9. Direct Effect between Variables

Sampel bisa 369, var 4 kues 7,7,7,7 =28.txt *SAMPEL 369, VAR 4.splsm PLS Algorithm (Run No. 3) Bootstrapping (Run No. 2)

Path Coefficients

	Original Sample (O)	Sample ...	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistic...	P Values
Job Erafting_ -> Teacher Performance_	0.452	0.450	0.052	8.769	0.000
Leadership Style_ -> Job Erafting_	0.321	0.319	0.041	7.849	0.000
Leadership Style_ -> Teacher Performance_	0.342	0.344	0.038	8.990	0.000
Work Environment_ -> Job Erafting_	0.654	0.656	0.039	16.701	0.000
Work Environment_ -> Teacher Performance_	0.188	0.188	0.044	4.275	0.000

4.7 The Effect of Job Crafting on Teacher Performance

Job crafting has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance, this can be seen from the P value of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. This is in accordance with a study conducted by Svicher and Di Fabio (2021) which states that job crafting involves changes in the design of one's work, so that teacher performance will also change. These results are in line with the study of Setyawati and Nugrohoseno (2019) which states that if job crafting is implemented properly it will have a positive impact on increasing employee performance. Similar results were found in a study conducted by Sudibjo and Widiastuti (2021) which showed that job crafting had a positive relationship with teacher performance, and also a study conducted by Lee and Lee (2018) which indicated that job crafting showed a positive relationship with performance. The results of this study are also in line with the study of Lichtenthaler and Fischbach (2018) which shows that job crafting which focuses on promotion has a positive effect on employee performance, and is also in line with the study of Nguyen et al (2019). Based on the results of several studies from several journal references mentioned above, it was found that job crafting plays a role in performance.

4.8 The Effect of Leadership Style on Job Crafting

Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on job crafting. This can be seen from the P value of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. These results are consistent with a study conducted by Stevi Becher Sengkey ed al. (2016) which states that leadership style has an effect on job

crafting and with a study conducted by LATHIFATUL AZMI (2022) which indicates that there is an effect of leadership style on job crafting. Similar results were also found in a study conducted by MA Marcellino (2022) and a study conducted by Stevi Becher Sengkey (2016).

4.9 The Effect of Leadership Style on Teacher Performance

Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. This can be seen from the P value of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. These results are consistent with studies conducted by Lange and Alina (2020), Mahfud et al. (2021), and Mariatie et al (2021). The results of the study by Pawirosumarto et al (2017) show that leadership style has a significant effect on employee performance, and the study by Lutfiyanto et al (2020) states that leadership style has a significant effect on teacher performance. Widiastuti (2021) shows that empowering leadership has a positive relationship with teacher performance. The results of the research showing that leadership style has a significant effect on employee performance are found in the study of Mahfud et al, Safiri and Zaidin (2021). The results of the several journal references mentioned above confirm that leadership plays a role in performance, but different results are shown by the study of Giantoro et al. (2019) where it is stated that the leadership of the school principal has no influence on teacher performance.

4.10. The Effect of Work Environment on Job Crafting

Work Environment has a positive and significant effect on job crafting. This can be seen from the P value of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. These results are consistent with research conducted by Schoeman (2019) which shows that an active work environment can support or limit the job crafting process by providing detailed insight into the underlying dimensions of work pressure, autonomy and social climate, and their relationship to some job crafting processes. Mukhtar (2018) states that partially the work environment has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance, findings that are in line with a study conducted by Pawirosumarto et al (2017). and also a study by Sri Haryanti (2020). The research results from several reference journals are convergent to the finding that the work environment plays a role in performance. However, it is different from the results of the study by Pawirosumarto et al (2017) where it was found that the work environment had no effect on teacher performance, which is in line with the study conducted by Chang et al (2020) which shows that the work environment has no significant association with job crafting. From the description above, some say that the work environment has an effect on job erasing and some say it has no effect, but the present study shows a finding that the work environment has a significant effect on job crafting.

4.11 The Effect of Work Environment on Teacher Performance.

The work environment has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. This can be seen from the P value of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. These results are in accordance with a study conducted by Al-Omari and Okasheh (2017) which states that the work environment can be anything that is around the employee and can influence how the employee performs his duties because the work environment is a space where people can gather to do their job and achieve results. This result is also in accordance with the study of Massoudi and

Hamdi (2017) which states that the work environment can be shaped by physical conditions, such as office temperature, and equipment, such as personal computers, also it can be related to things such as work methods or procedures. Similar results were also found in a study conducted by Mukhtar (2018) which stated that partially the work environment had a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. Similar findings were also shown by several other studies, including the study of Anggrayni, Sawiji and Susantiningrum (2018) with the finding that there was a significant positive effect of the work environment on teacher performance, and Prihanto (2017) which showed that there was a significant influence of the work environment on teacher performance. In contrast to these studies, Nugraha (2020) shows that there is no effect of the work environment on teacher performance. The same results were obtained by Pawirosumarto et al (2017) indicating that the work environment has no significant effect on employee performance.

Table 10. Indirect Effect between Variables

The screenshot shows the 'Specific Indirect Effects' table from the SmartPLS software. The table has columns for the path, Original Sample Mean, Sample Mean, Standard Error, T-Statistic, and P-Value. Two paths are listed: Leadership Style -> Job Crafting -> Teacher Performance and Work Environment -> Job Crafting -> Teacher Performance. Both paths show a significant indirect effect with P-values of 0.000.

	Original ...	Sample ...	Standard ...	T Statistic...	P Values
Leadership Style -> Job Crafting -> Teacher Performance_	0.145	0.144	0.025	5.712	0.000
Work Environment_ -> Job Crafting -> Teacher Performance_	0.296	0.295	0.037	7.908	0.000

4.12 Job Crafting can Mediate the Effects of Leadership Style on Teacher Performance

This can be seen from the P value of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. This means that job crafting as an intervention variable allows teacher performance to encourage teachers to make voluntary changes either on their own initiative or involving management who can create decent jobs. These results are in accordance with a study conducted by Svicher and Di Fabio (2021) which indicates that job crafting involves changes in the design of one's work, so that thereby the teacher's performance will also change. In addition, if job crafting is implemented properly, it will have a positive impact on increasing employee performance (Setyawati and Nugrohoseno, 2019). The findings in this study are also in line with the study conducted by Sudibjo and Widiastuti (2021) which shows that job crafting has a positive relationship with teacher performance and is also in line with the study of Lee and Lee (2018) which indicates that job crafting shows a positive relationship with performance. Similar results were also found in the study of Lichtenthaler and Fischbach (2018) which stated that job crafting which focuses on promotion has a positive effect on employee performance which is also in line with the study of Nguyen et al (2019). The results of the research from the several journal references

mentioned above confirm that job crafting plays a role in mediating the effect of leadership style on teacher performance.

4.13 Job Crafting can Mediate the Effect of Work Environment on Teacher Performance

This can be seen from the P value of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. This means that job crafting as an intervention variable on the effect of teacher performance allows teachers to make voluntary changes either on their own initiative or involving management which can create decent jobs. These results are in accordance with the study conducted by Sudibjo and Widiastuti (2021) and with the study of Svicher and Di Fabio (2021). Furthermore, the results of a study by Moon et.al (2018) and also a study by Nguyen et al (2019) state that job crafting has an effect on employee performance. The results of the several journal references above confirm the finding that job crafting plays a role in mediating the effect of the work environment on teacher performance.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The conclusion that the researchers could find was that the variables of leadership style, work environment, and job crafting directly had a positive and significant effect on teacher performance, and indirectly job crafting could mediate the effect of the variables of leadership style and work environment on the performance of high school teachers in Medan City, North Sumatra, Indonesia.

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